

ISic3029

I.Sicily inscription 3029

Language

Ancient Greek and Latin(?)

Type

funerary

Material

basalt

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Probably recovered in the grounds of the property of the Di Mauro brothers, in contrada Diana, 'in una tomba a cassone, a circa 2 metri di profondita'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 65 cm

Width 41 cm

Depth 11 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Ποπλιλίου

2. [---]νάρου

3. Ϻ[---]

Apparatus

Text of ILipara, after Orsi (the last to have autopsy)

Moretti: [Ται]ναρου or [Νιν]ναρου; Manganaro: [Νικά]νδρου or [Μενα]νδρου

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645385

PHI 332349

PHI 334842

Bibliography

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